

Indo-Pacific dorid nudibranchs collected in Lebanon (eastern Mediterranean)

Nudibranchios doridáceos indo-pacíficos recolectados en el Líbano (Mediterráneo oriental)

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ABSTRACT

Plocamopherus ocellatus Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830, *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830) and *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) are reported from Lebanon for the first time. This is also the first confirmed report, based on anatomical examination, of these three species in the eastern Mediterranean. All specimens examined were fully mature and it is very likely that these three species have stable and reproductively active populations in the Mediterranean.

RESUMEN

Plocamopherus ocellatus Rüppell y Leuckart, 1830, *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell y Leuckart, 1830) y *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) se citan en el Líbano por primera vez. Además, estas son las primeras citas confirmadas con estudios anatómicos de estas tres especies en el Mediterráneo oriental. Todos los ejemplares examinados eran completamente maduros, por lo que es muy probable que estas tres especies tengan poblaciones estables y reproductivamente activas en el Mediterráneo.

KEY WORDS: Lessepsian immigrants, Nudibranchia, Doridoidea, *Plocamopherus ocellatus*, *Hypselodoris infucata*, *Discodoris lilacina*, Lebanon, eastern Mediterranean.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Inmigrantes Lessepsianos, Nudibranchia, Doridoidea, *Plocamopherus ocellatus*, *Hypselodoris infucata*, *Discodoris lilacina*, Líbano, Mediterráneo oriental.

INTRODUCTION

Since the early eighties, a small but steadily increasing number of Indo-Pacific opisthobranch species have been reported from the Mediterranean Sea. These Lessepsian immigrants have been mostly found in the coasts of Israel, Turkey, and Lebanon, in the eastern

Mediterranean (BARASH AND DANIN, 1977; MIENIS AND GAT, 1981; GAT AND MIENIS, 1981; BARASH AND DANIN, 1982; 1986; BOGI AND KHAIRALLAH, 1987; AARTSEN, CARROZZA AND LINDNER, 1990; BOGI AND GIANNINI, 1990; GAT, 1993; ÇEVİK AND ÖZTÜRK, 2001). Some of

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these records are unconfirmed due to the absence of anatomical studies or voucher specimens available in scientific institutions.

The present paper deals with a small collection of opisthobranchs collected in Lebanon by Ghazi Bitar and Helmut Zibrowius, and constitutes the first confirmed report of some Lessepsian immigrants. These opisthobranchs were made available to us by the collectors including brief descriptions of the

external color, but without photographs or drawings of the living animals, so identifications were based on these notes and anatomical examination of preserved specimens. Illustrations of the external morphology of the preserved specimens have not been included. The material examined is deposited at the Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM) and the Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid (MNCN).

SPECIES DESCRIPTIONS

Family TRIOPHIDAE Odhner, 1941

Genus *Plocamopherus* Leuckart in Rüppell, 1828

Plocamopherus ocellatus Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830 (Figs. 1-2A)

Material examined: Chak El Hatab, between Hannouch and Selaata, Lebanon, 5 m depth, 4 June 2000, 1 specimen 22 mm preserved length (LACM 152716). Raoucheh, Lebanon, 7 m depth, 19 September 2002, 2 specimens 31 mm and 20 mm preserved length (MNCN 15.05/46581).

Description: Body elongate, with the foot extending far beyond the posterior end of the notum. Dorsal surface of the posterior end of the foot with a high irregular fin-like protuberance. Velum with 17 ramified appendages. On each side of the body there are two ramified lateral papillae anterior to the gill and two clusters of 2-3 knob-like organs posterior to the gill. Gill composed of five tripinnate branchial leaves. Rhinophores with 28 lamellae. Background color black with several large, irregular reddish spots.

Radular formula 16 x 11.3.1.3.11. There is a broad rachidian plate, which is traversed by a strong furrow and divided into several elongate tuberculate plates (Fig. 1A). The 3 innermost lateral teeth are hook shaped having a secondary cusp, and are similar in length (Fig. 1B). The 11 outermost lateral teeth are rectangular and decrease in size towards the margin of the radula. Jaws composed of numerous simple elements (Fig. 1C).

Reproductive system triaulic. Ampulla convoluted, branching into a short oviduct and the prostate (Fig. 2A). Oviduct entering the female gland mass

near its opening. Prostate large and flat; connecting with the deferent duct, which expands again into the ejaculatory portion. Muscular deferent duct and vagina opening into a common atrium. Vagina long and straight. At its proximal end the vagina joins the bursa copulatrix. From the bursa copulatrix leads another duct connecting with the uterine duct and the seminal receptacle. Bursa copulatrix oval in shape, about twenty times as large as the seminal receptacle.

Remarks: *Plocamopherus ocellatus* is a poorly known Red Sea species characterized by its external dark coloration with reddish or orange spots (ELIOT, 1908). ELIOT's (1908) is the only record of this species from the Red Sea after its original description by RÜPPELL AND LEUCKART (1828-30) [1830]. The features of our specimens agree with the original description and redescription, and there is no doubt they belong to the same species.

This species was recorded from the Mediterranean for the first time by BARASH AND DANIN (1982) in Nizzanim, Israel. The present study constitutes the second Mediterranean record, based on three specimens.

Figure 1. Scanning electron micrographs of the radula and jaws of *Plocamopherus ocellatus* Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830 (LACM 152716). A: general view of the radula; B: detail of a half-row; C: jaw elements. Scale bars, A: 1 mm; B, C: 200 μ m.

Figura 1. Fotografías de microscopio electrónico de barrido de la rádula y mandíbulas de Plocamopherus ocellatus Rüppell y Leuckart, 1830 (LACM 152716). A: vista general de la rádula; B: detalle de una semihileria; C: elementos de la mandíbula. Escalas, A: 1 mm; B, C: 200 μ m.

Family CHROMODORIDIDAE Bergh, 1891

Genus *Hypselodoris* Stimpson, 1855

Hypselodoris infucata (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830) (Figs. 2B, 3)

Material examined (localities in South to North order): Beyrouth Harbor, Lebanon, 2 June 2000, 3-8 m, 36 specimens 13-24 mm preserved length (LACM 152756) and 27 specimens 11-31 mm preserved length (MNCN 15.05/45958). Jbaíl, Lebanon, 17 October 1999, harbour entrance, 2-3 m, 1 specimen (MNCN 15.05/45959). Selaata, Lebanon, 2 May 2001, 1 specimen 8 mm preserved length (LACM 152757). El Heri, Lebanon, 2-3 m depth, 3 June 2000, 2 specimens 7-10 mm preserved length (LACM 152758). Ramkine Island, off Tripoli, Lebanon, 31 May 2000, 4 specimens 12-22 mm preserved length (LACM 152755).

Description: Body elongate and relatively high in profile, with the foot extending far beyond the posterior end of the notum. Dorsum smooth. Gill composed of 11 unipinnate branchial leaves and rhinophores with 15 lamellae in a 20 mm preserved length specimen (LACM 152756). Background colour blue or greenish blue. There may be darker and lighter areas irregularly distributed on the dorsum. In some specimens the blue color fades to paler blue in the middle of the dorsum. Dark blue and yellow spots scattered over the entire dorsum.

Radular formula $54 \times 62.0.62$. Rachidian teeth absent. Innermost lateral teeth with two large cusps and a shorter denticle on the inner side of the cusp (Fig. 3A). Remaining lateral teeth hook-shaped, with two cusps and lacking denticles on both sides. Outer laterals are short, having 1-8 denticles situated under the second cusp (Fig. 3B). Jaws composed of numerous, simple elements.

Reproductive system triaulic. Ampulla elongated, branching into a short oviduct and the prostate (Fig. 2B). Oviduct entering the female gland mass

Figure 2. Reproductive systems (scale bars, 1 mm). A, B: *Plocamopherus ocellatus* Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830 (LACM 152716); C: *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830) (LACM 152755); D, E: *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) (LACM 152717). Abbreviations, am: ampulla; bc: bursa copulatrix; dd: deferent duct; fg: female glands; pr: prostate; sr: seminal receptacle; v: vagina; vg: vestibular gland.

Figura 2. Aparatos reproductores (escalas, 1 mm). A, B: Plocamopherus ocellatus Rüppell y Leuckart, 1830 (LACM 152716); C: Hypselodoris infucata (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830) (LACM 152755); D, E: Discodoris lilacina (Gould, 1852) (LACM 152717). Abreviaturas, am: ampolla; bc: bolsa copulatrix; dd: conducto deferente; fg: glándulas femeninas; pr: próstata; sr: receptáculo seminal; v: vagina; vg: glándula vestibular.

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of the radula of *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830). A: Inner lateral teeth; B: Outer lateral teeth. Scale bars, 20 μm .

Figura 3. Fotografías de microscopio electrónico de barrido de la rádula de *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830). A: Dientes internos; B: Dientes externos. Escalas, 20 μm .

near the center of the mass. Prostate long and tubular; connecting with a thinner duct that expands again into the ejaculatory portion of the deferent duct. Muscular deferent duct and vagina opening into a common atrium. Vagina long and folded. At its proximal end the vagina joins the bursa copulatrix. At mid-length the uterine duct and the seminal receptacle connect with the vagina. Bursa copulatrix oval in shape, about thirty times as large as the seminal receptacle.

Remarks: The material here examined is anatomically identical to Indo-Pacific specimens of *Hypselodoris infucata* recently re-described by JOHNSON AND VALDÉS (2001).

Hypselodoris infucata is a well-known Indo-Pacific immigrant in the Mediterranean. The first Mediterranean record

of this species was published by BARASH AND DANIN (1974) under the name *Glossodoris runcinata*. There are two subsequent records from Israel by GAT AND MIENIS (1981) and MIENIS AND GAT (1981). More recently ÇEVİK AND ÖZTÜRK (2001) reported *H. infucata* from southern Turkey; according to these authors *H. infucata* reached the coast of Turkey following the northbound current parallel to the coast of Palestine, Israel, Lebanon and Syria.

All the specimens examined were sexually mature and most likely reproductively active. The large number of specimens collected also indicates that this species has stable populations in the eastern Mediterranean, as suggested by BARASH AND DANIN (1986). In Beyrouth harbour the population is thriving in a highly polluted environment.

Figure 4. Scanning electron micrographs of the radula and jaws of *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) (LACM 152717). A: general view of the radula; B: inner lateral teeth; C: jaw elements. Scale bars, A: 500 μ m; B: 50 μ m; C: 10 μ m.

Figura 4. Fotografías de microscopio electrónico de barrido de la rádula y mandíbulas de *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) (LACM 152717). A: vista general de la rádula; B: dientes internos; C: elementos de las mandíbulas. Escalas, A: 500 μ m; B: 50 μ m; C: 10 μ m.

Family DISCODORIDIDAE Bergh, 1891

Genus *Discodoris* Bergh, 1877

Discodoris lilacina (Gould, 1852) (Figs. 2C-D, 4)

Material examined: El Heri, Lebanon, 2-3 m depth, 3 June 2000, 1 specimen 23 mm preserved length (LACM 152717).

Description: Body flat, oval, with the posterior end of the foot covered by the notum. Dorsum covered by numerous, small conical tubercles, which are larger near the central area. Gill composed of 9 tripinnate brachial leaves. Rhinophores with 12 lamellae. The single specimen was preserved so information on the color of the living animal is not available. The preserved specimen is brownish with several rounded or oval dark brown spots of different sizes, being

larger in the central region of the dorsum. Along the innermost sides of the mantle margin there are two lines of large, oval, black spots. Ventrally, the anterior border of the foot is grooved and notched. The ventral side of the foot and mantle margin are covered with numerous brownish spots of various sizes.

Radular formula 20 x 22.0.22. Inner and mid-lateral teeth hamate (Fig. 4A), with a single cusp and no denticles (Fig.

4B). Outermost teeth with an elongate cusp and also lacking denticles. Jaw composed of several small, irregular elements (Fig. 4C).

Reproductive system triaulic. Ampulla convoluted, branching into a short oviduct and the prostate (Fig. 2D). Oviduct entering the female gland mass near its opening (Fig. 2C). Prostate large and flat, with two distinct portions. The prostate connects with a thin duct that expands again into the ejaculatory portion of the deferent duct. Muscular deferent duct and vagina opening into a common atrium. Vagina long and convoluted. At its proximal end the vagina joins the bursa copulatrix. From the bursa copulatrix leads another duct connecting with the uterine duct and the seminal receptacle. Bursa copulatrix oval in shape, about ten times as large as the seminal receptacle.

Remarks: This is a widespread Indo-Pacific species collected in several localities from the Red Sea to Hawaii (see EDMUNDS, 1971), in most cases under the name *Discodoris fragilis* (Alder and

Hancock, 1864). *Discodoris fragilis* is currently regarded as a synonym of *D. lilacina* (RUDMAN, 1999). The reproductive anatomy and radula of the Indo-Pacific specimens studied by EDMUNDS (1971) and KAY AND YOUNG (1961), are identical to those of our material, and there is no doubt about the identity of the Lebanese specimen.

BARASH AND DANIN (1977) cited *Discodoris lilacina* from Israel for the first time (as *D. concinna*). It is most likely that the specimen studied by Barash and Danin belongs to the same species as our material from Lebanon, but their record is unverifiable due to the absence of anatomical studies. The present paper is the first confirmed Mediterranean record for *D. lilacina*.

Records of *Discodoris fragilis* from the Canary Islands by ORTEA, BACALLADO AND PÉREZ-SÁNCHEZ (1981) and Madeira by WIRTZ (1995) belong to *Discodoris confusa* Ballesteros, Llera and Ortea, 1985, a species similar in external morphology (see BALLESTEROS, LLERA AND ORTEA, 1985 and WIRTZ, 1999).

CONCLUSIONS

Three other Lessepsian opisthobranchs have been recorded from Lebanon by BOGI AND KHAIRALLAH (1987) and BOGI AND GIANNINI (1990), all of them belonging to the Cephalaspidea: *Pyrrunculus fourieri* (Audouin, 1826) (as *Retusa*), *Cylichnina girardi* (Audouin, 1826), and *Acteocina mucronata* (Philippi, 1849).

This is the first confirmed record in the Mediterranean of *Plocamopherus ocellatus* Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830, *Hypselodoris infucata* (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1830) and *Discodoris lilacina* (Gould, 1852) based on anatomical examination. It also constitutes the first anatomical study of *Plocamopherus ocellatus*, which was only known from external descriptions (Rüppell and Leuckart, 1828-30; Eliot, 1908). All specimens examined were fully mature and it is very likely that these three species have stable and reproductively active populations in the Mediterranean.

The present paper is a contribution to the atlas of exotic mollusks introduced in the Mediterranean, which is now ready for publication (ZENETOS, GOFAS, RUSSO AND TEMPLADO, in press), and it will include full color figures of the external morphology of all species. An electronic version of the atlas is currently available in the web site of the CIESM (International Commission for the Scientific Exploration of the Mediterranean Sea): <http://www.ciesm.org/atlas>.

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